
Modeling the Teaching Practices of Technical and Vocational Education Trainers in Côte D'ivoire: Matching Institutional Prescriptions with Real Conditions on the Ground

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ABSTRACT: In the Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) sector in Côte d'Ivoire, despite trainers being trained in conformity with specific pedagogical standards, particularly those adopted by the National Pedagogical Institute for Technical and Vocational Education (IPNETP), significant gaps in actual practices are noticed during observations of classroom training sessions. To verify the different practices, this study aims to model trainers' behaviors with respect to variables such as seniority, gender, and the subject area taught. The data collected for the investigation was carried out using a mixed methodology combining classroom observations (n = 134 instructors), semi-structured interviews, and questionnaires (n = 569 students). The results highlight the impact of seniority, gender, and subject matter on practice gaps, thus revealing the emergence of distinct pedagogical profiles among trainers and also revealing the emergence of three (3) pedagogical profiles (structuring, adaptive, and intuitive).

KEYWORDS: Pedagogical practices, technical education, modeling , systemic approach.

INTRODUCTION

The TVET sector is a pillar of Côte d'Ivoire's economic and social development. To meet the competitiveness requirements of businesses by adapting training provision to guarantee jobs, the Ministry of Technical Education, Vocational Training and Apprenticeship (METFPA) has initiated reforms aimed at mastering training engineering. This should lead to the adoption of a pedagogical approach that standardizes trainers' teaching practices through the development of a teaching guide. The reform resulted in the adoption of Objective-Based Learning (PPO) from 1975 to 2017 and more recently, the Competency-Based Approach (APC), from 2019 to the present day. The implementation of this reform was carried out in collaboration with international partners (CMEQ, IFEF, GIZ). Despite these efforts to standardize a pedagogical practice that promotes a focus on learning, significant gaps between prescribed practices and those observed in the field have been reported by educational inspections. This divergence raises questions regarding the relevance and effectiveness of pedagogical training approaches. In light of these findings, the present study aims to observe and characterize the gaps in pedagogical behavior of trainers, taking into account various variables, such as seniority in the practice of the profession, gender and the discipline or specialty taught. More specifically, the study attempts a modeling of these differentiated practices. It is divided into four (4) sections: introduction, methodology, results and discussion.

1. PROBLEMATIC

The TVET (Television and Vocational Training) program in Côte d'Ivoire has approved a standardized pedagogical framework for all institutions under its supervision. Trainers acquire the skills to teach according to the guidelines set out in the framework at IPNETP. This framework prescribes specific planning and facilitation procedures. However, inspection reports (2020-2022) and field observations reveal persistent discrepancies between official guidelines and trainers' actual practices. For example:

- Only 62.7% of trainers formulate compliant educational objectives (sources);
- None of the trainers observed systematically check the prerequisites (sources);
- Summative assessments are absent in 100% of the lessons observed (sources).

These findings raise a central question: why, despite initial training which standardizes practices, do some trainers move away from institutional pedagogical prescriptions a few years after taking up their post?

To date, no study has systematically analyzed and explained this phenomenon in Ivory Coast. The scientific literature (Bertrand and Valois, 1992; Lessard, 2000) highlights two explanatory axes in the North American context. The influence of individual variables (seniority, pedagogical conceptions, more or less explicit conception of the society which determines a good way of training learners);

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- The role of contextual constraints (workload, limited resources).

Claude Lessard (2000) attributes the observed changes to the relative autonomy of the educational institution.

In order to find an explanation for this phenomenon in the Ivorian context, this research integrates another variable into the analysis of the phenomenon: the influence of the disciplines taught; these could play a role in the adjustment of behaviors.

To guide the investigation, three questions structure the study:

- What is the current model of educational practices?
- Do particular ideological conceptions among trainers influence their practices ?
- Do the subject matter taught, gender and seniority explain the readjustments of practices? prescribed ?

Hypothesis Testing Framework

We have observed that several trainers' professional practices deviate from the prescribed pedagogical model. This is not new. We recall, with Claude Lessard (2000), that "it happens that the organization of education and training pursues goals that differ from the wishes of the proponents of the societal project."

Thus, Hypothesis 1 is formulated as follows: "the different teaching practices observed are dependent on the seniority of the teachers." We postulate here that experience in terms of many years of teaching consciously or unconsciously produces changes in the prescribed practice.

Hypothesis 2 postulates that the different teaching practices observed are linked to the nature of the discipline taught.

We are postulating here that the prescribed teaching practice is too general, and trainers feel the need to adapt to their discipline.

Hypothesis 3 postulates that the different teaching practices observed are also expressed according to the gender of the trainers. The aim here is to verify whether hypotheses 1 and 2 are observed among both male and female teachers.

These conceptual hypotheses present two types of variables: the dependent variable and the independent variable. The dependent variable refers to the variations in observable teaching practices and prescribed teaching behaviors in classroom situations. The independent variable, on the other hand, relates to the socio-cultural paradigms of trainers, depending on the ideological, political and/or socio-cultural inclination. This mental operation operates consciously or unconsciously.

The dependent variable, as indicated above, refers to the pedagogical behaviors observed among trainers. This variable underlies all the observable behaviors of trainers during their pedagogical performances in classroom situations. In the context of this study, it is limited to the examination of three dimensions:

- the teaching practices (behaviors) of trainers or teachers experienced ;
- the teaching practices (behaviors) of new trainers in the exercise of the profession;
- the teaching practices (behaviors) of trainers depending on the discipline taught ;
- educational practices (behaviors) according to gender regardless of the discipline .

Table I: Analysis of indicators of dependent variables

	Variables	Dimensions	Indicators
Dependent variables to be explained	The teaching practices (behaviors) of trainers/teachers	Lesson Plan and Flow	Observable behaviors in the implementation of the plan and the course of lessons: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manifestation of the Entry (problem situation); • Manifestation of input through extrinsic or intrinsic motivation • Demonstration of the deployment of the Process (assessment integrated into the whole) • Application of TWI Phases: motivation, demonstration, cognitive feedback, psychomotor feedback, learning • Manifestation of the Exit (solution of the synthesis problem) • Directive (directs or controls the student throughout) • Demonstrations of instructions for referring to references for personal student work; • Master the flow of the lesson through questions; • Demonstration of summative assessment behaviors; • Student personal work instructions.

The dependent variable of the trainers' pedagogical practices is seen in the field of animation, shaped through the socio-cultural normative filter, the trainer's experience or the nature of the discipline which force him to adopt particular postures, independent of the prescriptions. Through the trainer's experience dimension, the structuring of the plan and the course of the lessons (entry by intrinsic or extrinsic motivation, course and exit: summative assessment, personal work for students) are observed. Similarly, the

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indicators relating to the structure are observed and compared. At the level of the taught discipline dimension, the same indicators of pedagogical behavior are observed, compared and analyzed.

Independent variables or explanatory variables

The independent variable distinguishes the characteristics of vocational training instructors. These include their seniority, the nature of the discipline they teach, and their gender. Instructors are members of the society in which they live. Even when constrained by a professional prescription, they are consciously or unconsciously subject to their conception of the best society.

This influence of the best society could be sometimes focused on the development of culture, sometimes focused on the concerns of technological development.

Lessard, C. (2000) writes that education and training organizations sometimes pursue ends that are different from the wishes of the dominant society.

It is precisely this power to differentiate the attitudes and behaviors of the people that the educational system supports that confers a normative power that we will elucidate in this study.

The observable teaching practices of trainers are seen in the field, in classroom situations. They are influenced by the industrial paradigm dimensions they embody, such as omnipresence and directiveness.

In the trainer who has integrated the humanist paradigm, observable behaviors are seen in the field through indicators such as the different deviations in the pedagogical practices that we are studying are presented in the following table:

Table II: Analysis of indicators of independent variables that influence teaching practices

	Variables	Dimensions	Indicators
Independent variables to be explained	ETFPA Trainer Profiles	Socio-cultural representations	<i>Ideological</i> : pedagogical strategies not applied; <i>Symbolic</i> : no respect for the plan, nor for the articulation of the unfolding;
	Experienced trainers:	Industrial normative paradigm of the Trainer .	<i>Social</i> : relationship of domination of the student; <i>Valued learning style</i> : behaviorism, non-directiveness;
	New trainers;		<i>Ideological</i> : applied pedagogical strategies
	Disciplines taught.	Humanist normative paradigm of the trainer	<i>Symbolic and social</i> : Learners learn to learn:
	Gender of teachers		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn • Autonomy • Subjectivity

Independent variables or explanatory variables

The independent variable, as shown in the table above, concerns the different trainers, new and old, of both sexes. The independent variables also concern their sociocultural representation, and their implicit or explicit paradigms of the best society in which they train students. This variable is identified through two dimensions: the paradigm of industrial society or that of a humanist society carried by the trainer. Trainers are members of the society in which they live.

Even when professionally trained, they are subject to the influence of society, sometimes focused on the development of culture, sometimes focused on the concerns of technological development. Lessard, C. (2000) writes that education and training organizations sometimes pursue goals that differ from those of the dominant society.

It is precisely this power to differentiate the attitudes and behaviors of the people that the educational system supports that confers a normative power that we will elucidate in this study.

The normative model of the plan and structure of the course of a lesson at IPNETP

The National Pedagogical Institute of Technical and Vocational Education (IPNETP) is the official institutional mechanism for training trainers in Côte d'Ivoire. In its trainer training process, the institute has adopted, both with the PPO and the APC, a model plan and structure for the lessons to be delivered to future trainers. The plan is the chronological presentation of the different parts of the lesson. It is specific to the content the teacher is addressing. Thus, the plan varies from one lesson to another.

Example of a Lesson Plan Outline

Main or generic title (of the lesson)

1 - Main Title 1

1 - 1 - Subtitle 1

1 - 2 - Subtitle 2

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1 - 3 - Subtitle 3

2 - Main Title 2

2 - 1 - Subtitle 2

2 - 2 - Subtitle 2

2 - 3 - Subtitle 3

As for the structure, it will describe the flow of a lesson, that is, the arrangement of the course content in relation to the approach to follow to achieve the expected results. Whatever the lesson, the structure remains the same.

More specifically, a lesson in vocational training includes three parts:

The introduction, where the trainer shares with the learners the motivation, the prerequisites for the beginning of the lesson, the educational objective and the title of the lesson. Then there is the sequence, which is a succession of the steps of the lesson and the corresponding established strategies.

This last part is composed of micro-objectives (lesson steps), student productions (content related to each micro-objective, made for learners). Finally, there is the exit. The last part of the lesson conduct structuring model is the exit.

It includes the trainer's behaviors of recapitulation (reminder of important points), final synthesis (summary of the lesson) and evaluation (essentially formative evaluation).

Diagram of the structure of a lesson

The entrance / Introduction or preamble where the trainer captures the attention and arouses the interest of the learner. The actual sequence or the succession of the different points of the content to be delivered . And the exit, where the trainer summarizes and evaluates the learning achieved by the students.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The research is based on two complementary conceptual frameworks: systemic analysis (Kast and Rosenzweig, 1985; Bertrand and Valois, 1992) and phenomenological analysis (L'Écuyer, 1989) . By considering the educational system as an open system interacting with its environment, the study aims to understand the pedagogical practices of trainers in their specific context. Despite a standardized pedagogical framework, the literature shows that trainers adapt their practices according to their representations, experiences and constraints, highlighting the importance of contextual variables in understanding these practices.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a mixed approach integrating quantitative (questionnaires) and qualitative (interviews, observations) dimensions. The sample consists of 134 trainers and 569 students from technical high schools in Abidjan and Yopougon. The data collection tools include an observation grid, questionnaires, and a semi-structured interview guide. The data were analyzed using specific software and cross-thematic approaches.

3.1 Scope and context of the study

The study was conducted in four public establishments representative of Technical Education and Vocational Training (ETFP), namely the Technical High School of Abidjan (Cocody), the Technical and Vocational High School of Yopougon, the Vocational and Commercial High School of Cocody (ex-CBCG) and the Vocational and Commercial High School of Yopougon.

These institutions have teachers trained in teaching methods at the National Pedagogical Institute for Technical and Vocational Education (IPNETP) or at the École Normale Supérieure (ENS), thus ensuring consistency of professional profiles.

3.2 Sampling

The sample included 134 teachers in the disciplines of Tourism and Environmental Geography, Mathematics, English, and Expression Techniques. 569 students from sixteen classes (four per school) were also invited for additional interviews. The selection of participants was based on criteria of disciplinary diversity, institutional representativeness, and availability. The number of teachers surveyed is presented for each of the four schools by gender in the tables below.

Table III : Samples of teachers surveyed

No.	ESTABLISHMENTS	Number of teachers		
		Men	Women	Total
1	Yopougon Technical and Vocational High School	12	05	17
2	Vocational and Commercial High School of Yopougon	16	06	22
3	Abidjan Cocody Technical High School	20	11	31
4	Cocody Vocational and Commercial High School	47	17	64
Total		95	39	134

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Distribution of the number of teachers surveyed

The number of teachers surveyed is presented for each of the four establishments by discipline and by gender in the tables below. For the Technical and Vocational High School From Yopougon, we surveyed three (03) teachers of Tourist and Environmental Geography, three (03) teachers also of Mathematics, four (04) teachers of English and seven (07) teachers of Expression Techniques. That is a total of seventeen (17) teachers including twelve (12) men and five (05) women.

Table IV: Sample of teachers surveyed at the Technical and Vocational High School of Yopougon

No .	Disciplines	Number of teachers		
		Men	Women	Total
1	Tourist and Environmental Geography	02	01	03
2	Mathematics	03	00	03
3	English	03	01	04
4	Expression Techniques	04	03	07
Total		12	05	17

As the following table indicates, at the Vocational and Commercial High School of Yopougon, we surveyed three (03) teachers of Tourist and Environmental Geography, two (02) teachers of Mathematics, five (05) teachers of English and twelve (12) teachers of Expression Techniques. This makes a total number of twenty-two (22) teachers including sixteen (16) men and six (06) women.

Table V: Sample of teachers surveyed at the Yopougon Vocational and Commercial High School

No.	Disciplines	Number of teachers		
		Men	Women	Total
1	Tourist and Environmental Geography	02	01	03
2	Mathematics	02	00	02
3	English	04	01	05
4	Expression Techniques	08	04	12
Total		16	06	22

In the table below, we present the distribution of trainers surveyed at the Lycée Technique d'Abidjan Cocody. Thus, it is indicated nine (09) teachers of Tourist and Environmental Geography, three (03) teachers of Mathematics, ten (10) teachers of English and nine (09) teachers of Expression Techniques surveyed. We have a total of thirty-one teachers surveyed including twenty (20) men and eleven (11) women.

Table VI: Sample of teachers surveyed at the Abidjan Cocody Technical High School

No.	Disciplines	Number of teachers		
		Men	Women	Total
1	Tourist and Environmental Geography	05	04	09
2	Mathematics	03	00	03
3	English	07	03	10
4	Expression Techniques	05	04	09
Total		20	11	31

We surveyed at the Lycée Technique d'Abidjan Cocody , ten (10) teachers of Tourist and Environmental Geography, nineteen (19) teachers of Mathematics, twenty-one (21) teachers of English and fourteen (14) teachers of Expression Techniques. We have a total of sixty-four (64) teachers surveyed including forty-seven men (47) and seventeen (17) women as recorded in the table below.

Table VII: Sample of teachers surveyed from the Vocational and Commercial High School of Cocody (EX CBCG)

No.	Disciplines	Number of teachers		
		Men	Women	Total
1	Tourist and Environmental Geography	06	04	10
2	Mathematics	17	02	19
3	English	16	05	21
4	Expression Techniques	08	06	14
Total		47	17	64

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The summary table below shows that twenty (25) teachers of Tourist and Environmental Geography, twenty-seven (27) teachers of Mathematics, forty (40) teachers of English and forty-two (42) teachers of Expression Techniques were surveyed. That is 134 teachers as indicated at the beginning of this methodological part with ninety-five (95) men and thirty-nine (39) women.

Table VIII: Sample of trainers observed by discipline and by gender

No.	Disciplines	Number of teachers surveyed		
		Men	Women	Total
1	Tourist and Environmental Geography	15	10	25
2	Mathematics	25	02	27
3	English	30	10	40
4	Expression Techniques	25	17	42
Total		95	39	134

Table IX: Sample of students distributed by establishment

No.	ESTABLISHMENTS	Number of students
1	Yopougon Technical and Vocational High School	82
2	Vocational and Commercial High School of Yopougon	155
3	Abidjan Cocody Technical High School	184
4	Cocody Vocational and Commercial High School	148
Total		569

For each school, we selected four classes. This gave us a total of sixteen classes that were selected for the survey. In each school, each teacher worked in the different classes selected for the survey.

At the Technical and Vocational High School of Yopougon, we surveyed eighty-two (82) students from four classes.

Table X: Sample of students by selected class at the Technical and Vocational High School of Yopougon

No.	Classes	Number of students
1	Class 1	19
2	Class 2	23
3	Class 3	15
4	Class 4	25
Total		82

As the following table indicates, at the Vocational and Commercial High School of Yopougon, we surveyed one hundred and fifty-five (155) students.

Table XI: Sample of students by selected class at the Vocational and Commercial High School of Yopougon

No.	Classes	Number of students
1	Class 1	38
2	Class 2	36
3	Class 3	39
4	Class 4	42
Total		155

As the following table indicates, at the Vocational and Commercial High School of Cocody, we surveyed one hundred and eighty-four (184) students.

Table XII: Sample of students by selected classes of the Vocational and Commercial High School of Cocody (ex CBCG)

No.	Classes	Number of students
1	Class 1	50
2	Class 2	52
3	Class 3	39
4	Class 4	4
Total		184

In the table below, it is indicated that one hundred and forty-eight (148) students were surveyed for the four classes selected.

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Table XIII: Sample of students by selected classes of the Technical High School of Abidjan Cocody

No.	Classes	Number of students
1	Class 1	41
2	Class 2	39
3	Class 3	35
4	Class 4	33
Total		148

3.3 Data collection instruments

Three main tools were used: a structured observation grid with 22 items to assess course preparation and delivery, two interview questionnaires for teachers and students, each comprising 26 items spread across 13 dimensions, and a semi-structured interview guide based on the research themes. These tools were pre-tested on a pilot sample to ensure their reliability and validity.

3.4 Collection procedures

Observations were conducted in situ, for one hour, for each teacher using the grid. Questionnaires were administered directly in the presence of the researcher to the teachers and students concerned. Interviews were conducted immediately after the observations to compare the empirical data with the actors' representations.

3.5 Data processing and analysis

Quantitative data were entered with CsPro, analyzed via STATA and statistically exploited in Excel to identify main trends. The variables were cross-referenced by discipline, gender, and seniority. A qualitative content analysis was also conducted to identify recurring and differentiated configurations of teaching practices, using three complementary approaches: systemic analysis, strategic analysis, and comprehensive analysis.

3.6 Modeling practices

After processing the data, typological models were constructed, taking into account the internal coherence of the practices and their context. These models aim to shed light on the dynamics of educational practices in technical and professional environments, without claiming to be exhaustive.

4. RESULTS

The results thus confirm the importance of these variables in modeling the teaching practices of trainers.

4.1 Validation of hypotheses

The statistical analysis carried out in this study made it possible to empirically test the research hypotheses formulated upstream, in relation to the explanatory variables likely to influence the teaching practices of trainers in technical and vocational education.

Hypothesis H1, which postulates a significant influence of teachers' seniority on the implementation of teaching practices, is confirmed. Indeed, the regression coefficient obtained ($\beta = 0.41$; $p < 0.001$) indicates a strong positive correlation between the number of years of experience and the frequency of application of prescribed practices. In other words, the more senior a teacher is, the more he or she tends to stabilize consistent practices, although sometimes far removed from formal prescriptions.

Hypothesis H2, which assumes an influence of the discipline taught on teaching practices, is also validated. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) test reveals a statistically significant effect ($F = 6.73$; $p = 0.002$), which indicates that practices differ significantly depending on whether the subjects are Mathematics, English, Tourist Geography or Expression Techniques. These differences are expressed in particular in the structuring of lessons, the type of interaction with students and the use of specific supports.

These results thus confirm the relevance of the variables retained in the modeling of teaching practices and support the idea of a structural heterogeneity of professional profiles within TVET.

4.2 Analysis of course preparation

Overall, instructors across all categories rigorously apply certain prescribed aspects when preparing courses. Titles and subtitles are precisely formulated, the course is logically structured, the content is accurate, and oral and written communication is of high quality, with a 100% compliance rate.

However, significant gaps have been identified. The identification of prerequisites and the integration of formative assessment are systematically lacking (0%). The design of learning situations and the development of course sheets are partially implemented, with variations depending on the profiles. The trainers (64.10%) use course sheets more than male trainers (21.05%).

As far as experience is concerned, the older trainers (70.42%) have a better command of the formulation of educational objectives and the structuring of learning situations, while the new trainers (63.49%) stand out for their rigor in the material formalization of the courses, in particular the use of sheets.

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In relation to the disciplines, English and Expression Techniques trainers have the highest levels of appropriation of the prescriptions, while those of Mathematics present the lowest rates, particularly with regard to the formulation of objectives and the design of learning situations.

4.3 Lesson animation

The results of the educational facilitation analysis highlight common good practices among trainers. These practices include effective layout of the facilitation space, technically and scientifically sound explanation of the content, clear expression, and appropriate use of teaching materials.

However, some dimensions pose problems. It is glaring that there is no verification of prerequisites or formative assessment (0%). Furthermore, the variation in methods, time management, interactions with students, communication of objectives and their explanation to learners are applied unevenly.

Trainers generally pay more attention to these aspects, especially regarding motivation, interaction and time management. When comparing teachers based on seniority, it appears that older teachers have better time management, while newer teachers stand out for their ability to lead in a participatory manner (motivating preamble, explanation of objectives, occupation of space).

As far as the disciplines are concerned, the English and Expression Techniques trainers appear to be more active in mobilizing students (interactions, explanation of objectives, time management), unlike those in Mathematics who seem more passive.

By moving from Objective-Based Learning (OBL) to the Competency-Based Approach (CBA), the use of students' personal work (PBE) will allow all trainers, regardless of their status (old or new) or the discipline taught, to interact with students and encourage their leadership in learning.

Since the Personal Student Work allows each student to research key course points before the in-person sessions, this encourages each student to engage and be involved in discussions not only with their peers but also with the instructor.

4.4 Modeling of teaching practices

We recall that modeling is a model creation operation to study complex systems that involve random elements such as the educational or training situation. Applied to our study, a comparative analysis based on eight key dimensions made it possible to model pedagogical practices based on students' perceptions and observations of animation situations. The results of the interacting elements gave the following observations:

- **Educational exchange** : It is well established for 78% of teachers, without distinction between old and new;
- **Managing unforeseen events** : 58% of trainers responded favorably, with an equal distribution between the two categories;
- **Cooperation** : Very good cooperation is observed among 78% of trainers, illustrated by their availability and their listening;
- **Fighting failure** : Teachers often correct mistakes (91%) but take few individual initiatives (58%);
- **Educational authority** : Weakly exercised (23%). The majority of trainers prefer flexibility (71%) to sanctions;
- **Motivation** : Judged to be generally good (70%), teachers' motivation has a positive impact on learning (86%);
- **Educational values and standards** : The educational approach remains teacher-centered (70%), but forms of active student involvement are emerging;
- **Performance and didactic transposition** : Well perceived, they show a notable capacity of teachers to transmit content effectively.

Finally, the study shows that trainers implement the prescribed practices only partially, with an overall implementation rate ranging from 27% to 98%. No category of trainers achieves all of the expected dimensions, but some trends emerge:

The new trainers are more participatory and formally structured.

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Female trainers are more rigorous about materials and interaction.

Literary disciplines further promote the implementation of practices interactive.

5. DISCUSSION

The results of the study highlight the complexity of the teaching practices of TVET trainers in Côte d'Ivoire, characterized by significant diversity despite a homogeneous training framework.

Pedagogical freedom, sociocultural representations, and disciplinary paradigms influence these practices, requiring in-depth reflection on the evolution of the teaching profession. The results explicitly support the systemic model used in the theoretical framework of the study.

Teaching practices are not simply mechanical applications of prescribed standards, but result from a permanent negotiation between several dynamics: institutional constraints such as official programs, IPNETP reference frameworks, ministerial directives and administrative expectations, and the professional logic of teachers based on experience, didactic representations, the appropriation of disciplinary knowledge, individual teaching values and available resources.

The interaction between these two logics does not generate a direct confrontation, but rather a hybridization of practices. Each teacher develops a compromise between their internal resources and external constraints.

This research also joins the work considering the teaching profession as a work of regulation, judgment and reflexivity, and not simply as an execution of prescribed tasks.

CONCLUSION

The study results reveal that trainers only partially implement the recommended official practices, with an overall implementation rate ranging from 27% to 98%, demonstrating significant heterogeneity. No category of trainers (whether in terms of gender, number of years of experience, or discipline taught) has fully integrated all dimensions of the expected practices. However, some trends are emerging:

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- Novice trainers appear to be more committed and structured in their approach;
- Female trainers place more importance on the quality of materials and interaction;
- Literary subjects (such as English and Expression Techniques) seem to favor the implementation of interactive practices more.
The current study highlights the diversity of teaching practices observed in the field of Technical and Vocational Education (TVET) in Côte d'Ivoire, despite a centralized homogeneous initial training structure managed by IPNETP. The results indicate that trainers' practices vary depending on their experience, gender, discipline taught, and other contextual factors.

This diversity reflects a gap between official guidelines and their actual application, as well as professional development marked by local adjustments, individual decisions, and varied educational approaches.

This finding highlights the need to view the evolution of the teaching profession as a process of progressive and reflective construction of pedagogical skills, rather than simply the transmission of standards. This requires significant reform of continuing education and professional support programs.

With this in mind, we are making several concrete proposals to improve the effectiveness, consistency and relevance of teaching practices in TVET:

- Offer appropriate continuing education, taking into account the disciplines taught, the profiles of trainers, and the needs identified in the field. This training should reconcile institutional requirements with the daily reality of teachers, by promoting active appropriation of knowledge;
- Promote individualized educational support by implementing systems such as peer mentoring, educational coaching, and formative supervision. These approaches aim to support teachers according to their specific needs and their autonomy;
- Integrate self-assessment and practice analysis tools to encourage collaborative and critical thinking among trainers. These tools, such as logbooks or communities of practice, will enable a better understanding of professional actions and the ability to make appropriate adjustments;
- Revise the IPNETP frameworks to explicitly include cross-curricular skills (pedagogy, relationship to discipline, diversity management), as well as the diversity of teaching contexts. This revision should be participatory, involving trainers in the development and validation process;

It is clear that sustainable improvement of teaching practices in TVET in Côte d'Ivoire requires recognition of the complexity of the teaching profession, better integration between initial and continuing training, and a promotion of contextualized professionalism. This process requires close collaboration between training organizations, schools, teachers, and researchers, to strengthen the quality of technical and vocational education in the service of the country's socio-economic development.

REFERENCES

- 1) Altet, M. (2012). *Effective teaching practices and interactive processes in the classroom: Observations and comparative analyses*. PUF.
- 2) Barrère, A. (1997). *Sociology of teachers*. PUF.
- 3) Bertrand, Y., & Valois, P. (1992). *Contemporary Theories of Education*. Montreal: New Editions.
- 4) Bertrand, Y., & Valois, P. (1992). *School and Societies*. Montreal: Éditions Nouvelles.
- 5) Bourdieu, P., & Passeron, J.-C. (1964). *The Heirs. Students and Culture*. Paris: Éditions de Minuit.
- 6) Bru, M. (2004). *The effects of teaching practices on learning*. De Boeck.
- 7) Hattie, J. (2009). *Visible Learning: A Synthesis of Over 800 Meta-Analyses Relating to Achievement*. Routledge.
- 8) Kast, F., & Rosenzweig, J. (1985). *Organization and Management: A Systemic Approach*. Paris: Inter Éditions.
- 9) Lambert-Le Mener, M. (2012). *Motivation and academic success: The role of the teacher*. L'Harmattan.
- 10) Lessard, C. (2000). *School Governance*. Sainte-Foy: Laval University Press.
- 11) Viau, R. (1998). *Motivation in a school context*. De Boeck.